

Divalent Metal Chelates of Macrocycle derived from Dihydrazide and Aromatic Diketone

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Manuscript received 6 December 1993, revised 18 April 1994, accepted 6 February 1995

Metal chelates of a macrocycle derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine have been prepared and characterised by chemical analysis, magnetic moments, conductance, electronic and infrared spectral studies.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) correspond to the stoichiometry $[M(C_{20}H_{22}N_{10}O_2)]X_2$, where $M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} , $X = Cl, Br, NO_3$ and NCS . Molar conductances of the iron, cobalt and nickel chelates (136.2–252.0 $\Omega\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) show that they are 1 : 2 electrolytes. The tests for anions are positive, directly indicating their presence outside the coordination sphere.

The ir spectra of the complexes indicate that amide group neither coordinates through nitrogen nor through oxygen of the amide group¹. On comparing the spectra of the metal chelates with hydrazones of heterocyclic aldehydes, the bands at 1 580–1 640 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ν_{CN} modes. A strong band observed at 1 630 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 1 610 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching modes of azomethine linkage². The vibrations are present at a lower range and indicate that nitrogen of azomethine group is coordinated to the metal atoms. This has been further confirmed by the appearance of ν_{M-N} vibration in the far-infrared spectra.

The four $\nu_{C=C}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ pyridine skeletal bands are observed at 1 590–1 610 (band I), 1 560–1 580 (band II), 1 450–1 490 (band III) and 1 430–1 440 cm^{-1} (band IV). On coordination with bivalent metal ions, a general shift of 2–4 cm^{-1} has been observed in almost every band in the spectra of the chelates. But the band at ~1 580 cm^{-1} shows an upward shift (10–15 cm^{-1}). The increase in the $C=C$ or $C=N$ stretching vibration (originating from the pyridine ring) is indicative of pyridine nitrogen coordination to the metal atom³. The shifting of ring breathing mode vibration from 990 cm^{-1} to 1 015–1 020 cm^{-1} also suggests pyridine nitrogen coordination. Two strong bands are observed in the spectra of the pyridine-based ligands at 795 and 730 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu(C-N)$ and $\phi(C-C)$ modes respectively. The splitting of band ~730 cm^{-1} into two components (720 and 755 cm^{-1}) again indicates pyridine nitrogen coordination to the metal atom⁴. The increase in the frequency

of (C–C) deformation mode from ~400 to ~415–435 cm^{-1} also indicates pyridine nitrogen coordination⁵.

The infrared spectra do not exhibit any bands at 3 200–3 400 cm^{-1} (NH_2), indicating the absence of NH_2 group in the chelates. The absence of stretching and bending modes of free carbonyl group (~1 700 cm^{-1}) indicates that this group is not present in the chelates.

Therefore, the data indicate that the NH_2 groups of carbohydrazide have condensed with carbonyl groups of 2,6-diacetylpyridine giving rise to a 20-membered macrocycle containing 10-nitrogen atoms suitably placed for coordination. Also, neither nitrogen nor oxygen of the amide group takes part in coordination but pyridine nitrogen and azomethine nitrogen atoms participate in coordination making four five-membered and two six-membered chelate rings.

The ionic halides do not exert any detectable effect on infrared spectra in the conventional region while ionic nitrate and thiocyanate show characteristic bands in this region⁶. The appearance of bands at ~1 350, 1 230 and 825 cm^{-1} assignable to NO_2 asymmetric, symmetric stretching and bending modes respectively, are compatible with ionic nitrate group⁷. This is further supported by the appearance of a sharp narrow band at ~1 770 cm^{-1} in these chelates. The bands at 2 310 and 2 110 cm^{-1} of the thiocyanate complexes due to ν_{NC} of NCS group suggest the ionic nature of thiocyanate group. This is further supported by the absence of a bending mode ~470 cm^{-1} characteristic of coordinated thiocyanate group.

Room temperature values of magnetic moments for the Mn, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu complexes are lie in 4.84–5.98, 5.42–5.58, 4.48–4.65, 2.96–3.10 and 1.78–1.88 B.M. respectively, corresponding to the high-spin distorted octahedral environment around the metal ions⁸.

The electronic spectra of the Mn chelates exhibit five weak bands at ~17 500–18 550, 20 250–21 100, 25 200–26 050 and 29 550 cm^{-1} , which are consistent with six-coordinate octahedral environment around the metal and can be interpreted in terms of D_{4h} symmetry. The spectral bands arising from sextet quartet $t_{2g}^3e_g^2$ configuration have been assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ (17 500–18 550), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ (21 100), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(G)$ (25 200), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$

NOTE

TABLE I

'Compd.*/(Colour)	Metal% Found / (Calcd)	D_q	D_t	DT	DQ	$\frac{DT}{DQ}$
[Mn(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Cl ₂] (Brown)	9.76 (9.82)					
[Mn(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Br ₂] (Brown)	- (8.47)					
[Mn(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂] (Brown)	8.85 (8.97)					
[Mn(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NCS) ₂] (Brown)	9.00 (9.09)					
[Fe(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(Cl ₂)] (Brown)	9.80 (9.98)					
[Fe(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Br ₂] (Brown)	8.50 (8.61)					
[Fe(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂] (Green)	9.00 (9.12)					
[Fe(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NCS) ₂] (Brown)	9.20 (9.24)					
[Co(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Cl ₂] (Pink)	10.50 (10.46)					
[Co(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Br ₂ Br ₂] (Red)	8.90 (9.03)					
[Co(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂] (Red)	9.50 (9.56)					
[Co(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NCS) ₂] (Pink)	9.58 (9.69)					
[Ni(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Cl ₂] (Blue)	10.00 (10.46)	1 175	211	2 859	28 928	0.09
[Ni(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Br ₂] (Green)	9.00 (9.03)	1 200	222	3 008	29 439	0.10
[Ni(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂] (Green)	9.50 (9.56)	1 230	228	3 089	30 168	0.10
[Ni(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NCS) ₂] (Green)	10.00 (9.69)	1 220	285	3 862	28 979	0.13
[Cu(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Cl ₂] (Green)	9.20 (9.50)	1 530				
[Cu(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)Br ₂] (Green)	8.20 (8.19)	1 455				
[Cu(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂] (Blue)	8.50 (8.57)	1 600				
[Cu(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₂)(NCS) ₂] (Blue)	4.00 (8.79)	1 585				

*C, H, N and X analyses were found satisfactory.

(D) (27 050) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ (D) ($\sim 29\,550\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The lower energy bands assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}$ (G), ${}^4T_{2g}$ (G) and ${}^4A_{2g}$ (G) have been used to evaluate the higher energy bands. The values of B and D_q are quite close to those reported earlier⁹.

The iron complexes exhibit bands at 8 510–8 900 and 11 450–12 550 cm^{-1} . The bands are the splitting of a single

band and may be assigned to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_{1g}$. It appears that the splitting of the spin-allowed band is attributable to John-Teller effect. However, the spectra is characteristic of a distorted octahedral geometry¹⁰. The cobalt chelates show bands at $\sim 8\,100$ – $9\,100$ (ν_1), $15\,250$ – $15\,750$ (ν_2) and $18\,700$ – $20\,250$ cm^{-1} (ν_3). The spectra resemble octahedral environment¹⁰. The spectra show a band in visible region and split due to the presence of low symmetry fields.

Thus, assuming the effective geometry to be D_{4h} , various bands may be assigned to transitions ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1) ($\sim 8\ 100$ – $9\ 100\ \text{cm}^{-1}$), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (F) (ν_2) ($\sim 15\ 250$ – $15\ 750$) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_3) ($18\ 700$ – $20\ 250\ \text{cm}^{-1}$). The assignment is correct⁹ in view of the ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.73–1.881). The values of D_q , B and β are calculated is given in the table. The spectrochemical series of anions can be drawn as $\text{NCS} > \text{NO}_3 > \text{halides}$.

The solution spectra of the nickel chelates exhibit a band $\sim 11\ 700$ – $12\ 300\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ with a shoulder on low energy side. The other two bands observed at $16\ 700$ – $17\ 100$ (ν_2) and $27\ 800$ – $28\ 250\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3) are assigned to transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3), respectively. The first two bands are split of one band (ν_1) and are in the range $9\ 700$ – $10\ 300$ and $11\ 750$ – $12\ 300\ \text{cm}^{-1}$, and may be assigned to transitions to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow E_g$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ (components of ${}^3T_{2g}$ in O_h symmetry). The values of ligand field parameters $D_1 > D_q^x$ and D_q^2 are calculated¹¹.

The higher energy band at $\sim 34\ 500\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ present in the spectra may be due to π – π^* transition of (C=N) group of the ligand. The values of absolute ligand parameters DT and DQ have been calculated¹⁰ (Table 2). The amount of distortion has been calculated in terms of DT/DQ. The values indicate that the complexes are moderately distorted with the increases in order of $\text{NCS} > \text{NO}_3 > \text{Br} > \text{Cl}$, which is in accordance with their order in nephelauxetic series.

The spectra of the copper chelates show bands at $17\ 700$ – $19\ 600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ with a shoulder on low energy side $14\ 550$ – $16\ 000\ \text{cm}^{-1}$. The spectra are comparable to those observed for octahedral complexes reported earlier¹². This indicates that the complexes are distorted octahedral¹². The separation of the spectral bands is of the order $\sim 2\ 500\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ and is consistent with the proposed geometry of the complexes, and the shoulder may assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and the broad band contains both ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ transitions¹³. The amount of distortion can not be calculated as the bands do not split.

The far-ir spectra of the chelates show bands at ~ 415 and $600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ assignable C=C out-of-plane and C=C in-plane deformations. These vibrations suffer significant shift towards higher frequencies and support pyridine nitrogen coordination to the metal atom¹⁴. The spectra also exhibit bands at 250 – 280 (Mn–Py), 265 (Fe–Py), 260 – 270 (Co–Py), 265 – 275 (Ni–Py) and 275 – $280\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (Cu–Py)^{5,15}. The bands at 360 , 315 , 325 – 335 , 425 – 440 , 445 – 465 and 475 – $515\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be tentatively assigned to Mn–N, Fe–N, Co–N, Ni–N and Cu–N (azomethine) stretching vibra-

tions¹⁶ and support azomethine nitrogen coordination. These values are well within the range reported for six-coordinate octahedral complexes.

Therefore, based on results, the following structure may be proposed for the chelates.

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